

Technical Design of New Camouflaged Monopole Telecommunication tower and Structural Behavior Study

Syed Ehtesham Ali¹, Dr. Mir Iqbal Faheem²

¹Research Scholar, School of Engineering & Technology, Career Point University, Kota,
Rajasthan, India

²Research Supervisor, School of Engineering & Technology, Career Point University, Kota,
Rajasthan, India

ABSTRACT

The objective of the proposed study is to design monopole towers, both with and without concealed heights, specifically at 30 meters. This design must adhere to a basic wind speed requirement of 39 meters per second, consistent with the latest ANSI/TIA-222-H specification. Research indicates that monopole towers exhibit superior structural conductivity compared to other types of lattice towers. This study is particularly significant as structural engineers are tasked with the complex challenge of designing and constructing telecommunication towers that can reliably support various loads in open weather conditions. Free-standing lattice towers are widely utilized globally. Recent surveys suggest a rapid increase in mobile towers due to the advent of 5G technology, which necessitates additional antennas on these structures. Many existing monopole towers are already burdened with numerous antennas, lacking the structural capacity to accommodate further loads. This research will explore innovative camouflaged designs for monopole towers aimed at enhancing their structural capacity and performance under new loading conditions. Additionally, environmental and economic considerations have prompted the exploration of improved design strategies to render communication towers more sustainable and cost-effective. Given their smaller dimensions and reduced space requirements for installation, monopole structures present a viable alternative to lattice towers.

Article Information

Received: 20th July 2024

Acceptance: 26th September 2024

Available Online: 10th October 2024

Keywords: Wind load, wind speed, ANSI/TIA-222-H code, antenna load, deflection, camouflaged polycarbonate material, Staad pro V8i.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid and significant rise in mobile phone usage in recent years has led to increased visibility for telecommunication companies and their infrastructure. Today, nearly every individual owns a mobile device, resulting in a heightened demand for communication services. Telecommunication towers serve as the most effective means to enhance local coverage and reliability. Civil engineers are responsible for assessing and designing these towers, which support panel antenna telecommunication equipment, platforms, and their

foundations. Expertise in civil engineering is crucial, as various components, including mounts, antennas, and additional accessories, are installed on the towers. Structural calculations for towers consider various loads, such as wind load and dead load. Telecommunication towers are categorized into different classes based on their cross-section, type of sections used, positioning, and structural dynamics. The classification reflects their structural behavior, leading to designations such as Guyed towers, Lattice towers, and Monopole towers. Monopole towers are particularly advantageous in space-constrained environments, as they are the most robust option for heights below fifty-five meters. Consequently, there is a significant demand for monopole towers within the telecommunications sector. Previous research has primarily focused on the structural performance of guyed towers, lattice towers with three and four legs, and monopole towers. Monopole towers are increasingly favored for connectivity purposes worldwide, especially given the challenges associated with securing land for traditional lattice tower construction; thus, a thorough examination of these structures is pertinent in the current landscape. Antennas will be accommodated within monopole towers ranging from 30 to 50 meters in height, thereby enhancing the coverage of these installations. Monopole towers offer versatility, as they can support antennas, lighting, and other applications. Investigating their design can lead to improvements and prolong the lifespan of the structures. A comprehensive analysis of the application of modern technologies in monopole towers will bolster their structural integrity.

II. RELATED WORKS

The following presents various theories and research conducted to date:

2.1 M. Pavan Kumar, P. Markhandrya Raju, M. Navyal, and G.T. Naidu (2017) examined two prevalent types of telecommunication towers in the construction industry: monopole and self-supporting towers. This paper compares the performance of monopole and self-supporting towers at various heights of 30m, 40m, and 50m under wind speeds of 33m/sec, 47m/sec, and 55m/sec. The STAAD(X) Tower program, specifically designed for analyzing telecommunication towers, is utilized to assess dead loads and wind loads during the evaluation of the antenna. The findings indicate that self-supporting towers exhibit smaller lateral displacements compared to monopole towers of equivalent height.

2.2 Riy Joseph (ISSN 2395-0095) and Jobil Varghese (2005) noted in their study that telecommunication towers are elevated structures typically designed to support parabolic antennas at specific heights. The structural engineer faces the challenging task of planning and erecting telecommunication towers that can effectively bear all loads in an outdoor environment. Lattice towers, which are freestanding, are commonly observed worldwide. Recent surveys indicate that the number of cell towers may surpass 500,000 by 2020. Acquiring land for the construction of these conventional lattice towers poses significant challenges in densely populated urban areas. The rapid increase in land prices has necessitated the development of environmentally sustainable alternatives to traditional lattice towers. Environmental and economic pressures have driven researchers to explore innovative methods for constructing communication towers that are both eco-friendly and cost-effective. Monopole systems are considered a more favorable option compared to lattice towers due to their reduced dimensions and smaller space requirements for construction. This study focuses on monopole mobile towers, utilizing the ANSYS finite element program for analysis. The ANSYS model is employed to predict the behavior of monopoles when utilized as

coordination towers, and the efficiency of the monopole tower is evaluated through finite element results.

2.3 Dimitrios V. Billionis and Dimitrios Vamvatsikos (2017) noted in their research that steel lattice towers are extensively utilized by telecommunication firms for the installation of radio wave dish antennas, facilitating network expansion. These structures are tall and highly optimized, designed to withstand severe weather conditions, including low temperatures, snow, and high winds, which are the primary loading factors. Notably, the combination of high winds and ice accumulation on the structural members and antennas significantly contributes to the risk of collapse. The study centers on a standardized model of a telecommunication tower employed by leading telecommunication companies in Greece. This model adheres to European Standards for regions situated within 10 kilometers of the coastline. The tower stands at 48 meters in height, featuring a square cross-section that tapers as it ascends, and is constructed using channel and angle steel sections. Non-linear dynamic analyses were conducted to evaluate the structure's fragility under wind and icing conditions. Wind loads were simulated through a three-dimensional wind field that accurately represented the spatial and temporal variations in wind speed across the tower's profile for various reference wind speed values. The effects of ice were analyzed by examining several uniformly thick ice layers, which increase both the weight and cross-sectional area of all structural members and antennas. The objective of this research is to develop fragility functions for all possible combinations of wind and icing conditions that may occur during the tower's operational lifespan. By integrating the relevant climatic hazard surfaces, the study estimates the risk of tower collapse throughout its anticipated lifetime, thereby providing a valuable decision-making tool for telecommunication companies regarding the necessity of replacing or upgrading their tower networks on an individual basis.

2.4 Prachi A. Uchade and P. O. Modani (2022) noted in their research that Lattice Towers are the predominant type of towers utilized in the construction sector. Recently, Monopole structures have also gained popularity as an alternative to lattice towers. This paper provides a comparative analysis of Monopole and Lattice Towers of varying heights. The analysis incorporates both dead loads and wind loads, utilizing STAAD Pro software, which is specifically designed for the evaluation of various structures and towers. The design and analysis of the towers are conducted on STAAD Pro, maintaining consistent height and loading parameters, followed by a comparison of the results obtained. Monopole structures represent a more advanced option, requiring less material and occupying less space for installation compared to lattice towers. Given the rising population and the escalating demand for land, along with its associated costs, there is a pressing need to innovate traditional lattice tower designs. Throughout this study, previous research that supports the analysis of towers has been thoroughly examined.

- Numerous studies and investigations have primarily focused on the structural behavior of simple monopole towers. This research aims to enhance the understanding of monopole structures, both camouflaged and non-camouflaged, and serves as a significant foundation for future comparative studies and applications of both types.
- Some researchers have noted that the implementation of new camouflaged technology in monopole towers results in increased lateral displacement and reduced structural capacity. This observation highlights a notable gap in the existing body of research.

- The introduction of innovative camouflaged technology in monopole structures has the potential to enhance their structural stability and lateral stiffness, indicating another area that requires further investigation.

III PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Figure 1. Summary of Project Flow

The illustration presented above indicates that the project will be executed in multiple phases, commencing with the selection of a title and concluding with the completion of the report. The chosen topic, “Technical Design of New Camouflaged Monopole Telecommunication Tower and its Structural Behavior,” highlights the significance of communication towers, particularly considering the limitations faced by monopole communication towers when subjected to increased antenna loads.

Gathering pertinent literature from libraries or online sources, including e-journals, research papers, and theses, significantly aids in comprehending the actual scenarios of tower design and performance. These relevant materials will serve as primary references and will also contribute to enhancing the current findings by providing additional facts and detailed figures, or by facilitating the discovery of new hypotheses related to the subject.

In the subsequent phase, the focus will be on examining the development of optimal geometry for tower design. This thesis investigates the methodologies employed to achieve the optimal design of a monopole telecommunication tower.

IV IMPLEMENTATION MODULE

The design process is divided into three stages. In the first stage, only the diameter of the tower is analyzed. The second stage involves a comprehensive analysis of the entire structure, considering both the diameter and thickness. The final stage is dedicated to selecting a tower design that ensures safety as a control model. However, there is potential for enhancement by evaluating both diameter and thickness, as these factors also influence the overall weight of the tower. A summary of the procedure is illustrated in the accompanying figure.

4.1 Antenna Loading and weight

S.NO	Description	NO's	Size(m)	Elevation(m)	Weight/Unit (Kn)	Total Weight
1.	30 Port Ant	3	2.769x0.469	35/30	0.7	2.10
2.	5G Ant	3	0.860x0.395	35/30	0.6	1.80
3.	RRU'S	24	0.48x0.356	35/30	0.25	6.00
4.	HP	2	0.6	35/30	0.18	0.36

4.2 Material properties and Anchor Bolt Specification

Material Properties adopted for analysis & design of Monopole	
Steel grade of shaft-ASTM -A572 GRADE 50 OR Equivalent	
Yield stress-345 N/mm ²	
Tensile Strength-448 N/mm ²	
Anchor Bolts adopted for analysis & design of Monopole	
Steel grade of shaft-ASTM -A572 GRADE 50 OR Equivalent	
Yield stress-345 N/mm ²	
Tensile Strength-448 N/mm ²	

4.3 Geometry of monopole:

Figure 2. Geometrical configuration of monopoles without camouflage and monopole with camouflage (height = 30m and basic wind speed = 39m/sec.)

A Steel Shaft flange connection has been considered in the design for both the monopole Tower and the Camouflaged Monopole Tower, which were analyzed using STAAD(V8I). Figure 2 illustrates the geometric configuration of the Monopole, both with and without camouflage, at a height of 30 meters, subjected to a basic wind speed of 39 m/sec.

4.4 Research design:

The design must adhere to the latest special design code ANSI/TIA-222-H-2017, which is a revision of ANSI/TIA-222-G, applicable to antenna telecom towers and small wind turbine support structures, as established by the Telecommunications Industry Association in Arlington, USA, and Canada.

1. The basic wind speed is set at 140.4 km/h, while the ultimate wind speed is 176.904 km/h.
2. Monopole deflection is limited to 4.0 degrees when subjected to an operational wind speed of 120 km/h.
3. The exposure category is classified as C.

4. The risk category is designated as II.

5. The topographic category is identified as I

4.5 Load Combination:

In accordance with ANSI/TIA-222-H, the minimum design load combinations for structures are as follows: 1.2 Dead Load (D.L) + 1.0 Wind Load (W.L) for section design, and 1.0 Dead Load (D.L) + 1.0 Wind Load (W.L) for serviceability.

4.6 Wind load:

The wind load applied to the monopole, both in its uncamouflaged form and with a camouflaged structure that conceals the loads and design structural parameters, was utilized for the structural analysis of towers subjected to wind loadings. This analysis was conducted using a spreadsheet for various heights and wind speeds, in accordance with ANSI/TIA-222-H.

WIND LOAD CALCULATION AS PER ANSI/TIA-222-H

Cross Section	CIRCULAR
Type of Tower	Pole
Height of Tower, h	30 m
Basic Design Wind Speed, V	39 m/s
Ultimate Wind Speed, V _{ult}	49.14 m/s
Exposure Category	C
Z _a	274 m
α	9.5
K _{z, min}	0.85
K _e	1
Topographic Factor	Category 1
K _{zt}	1
Ground Elevation Factor, K _g	1
Rooftop wind speed-Up Factor, K _r	1
Wind Direction Probability Factor, K _d	0.95
Risk Categorization of structure	II

Description	Surface Type	Height above ground level @ base of structure, z	Size of Appurtenances			NOS	Velocity Pressure Coefficient, k _z	Aspect Ratio, (L/W)	C	Force coefficient, C _f	Projected area of component of the Appurtenance, A _c	Velocity pressure, q _z (N)	Gust effect factor, G _{ff}	Effective Projected Area, (EPA) _A	Design Wind Force, F _A (kN)
			Length, L (m)	Dia. (D)/Width (W), m	Depth, D (m)										
Dia. 1.000mm Pole	Round	0.000	12.00	1.000	1.0000	1	0.850	12.00	45.305	0.60	12.000	1195.29	1.1	7.200	9.467
Dia. 0.725mm Pole	Round	12.000	12.00	0.725	0.725	1	1.040	16.55	36.332	0.60	8.700	1462.473	1.1	5.220	8.398
Dia. 0.475mm Pole	Round	24.000	0.50	0.48	0.48	1	1.204	1.05	25.612	0.50	0.238	1693.093	1.1	0.119	0.222
30 PORT ANT	Flat	30.000	2.769	0.469	0.469	3	1.262	5.90	25.890	1.35	1.299	1774.654	1.1	1.755	10.278
5G ANT	Flat	30.000	0.86	0.40	0.40	3	1.262	2.18	21.805	1.20	0.340	1774.654	1.1	0.408	2.388
24-RRU	Flat	30.000	0.48	0.356	0.356	24	1.262	1.35	19.652	1.20	0.171	1774.654	1.1	0.205	9.600
MW-0.60 DIA	Flat	30.000	0.60	0.60	0.6	2	1.262	1.20	33.122	1.20	0.360	1774.654	1.1	0.360	1.406

Description	Surface Type	Height above ground level @ base of structure, z	Size of Appurtenances			NO'S	Velocity Pressure Coefficient, k_z	Aspect Ratio, (L/W)	C	Force coefficient, C_f	Projected area of component of the Appurtenance, A_a	Velocity pressure, q_z (N)	Gust effect factor, G_H	Effective Projected Area, (EPA) A_e	Design Wind Force, F_d (kN)
			Length, L (m)	Dia (D)/ Width (W), m	Depth, D (m)										
30m MONOPOLE WITH CAMOUFLAGED															
CAMOUFLAGED	Round	30.000	5.00	2200	22000	1	1.262	2.27	121.447	0.50	11.000	1774.654	1.1	5.500	10.757

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Structural capacity of 30m monopole in terms of moment without camouflaged tower and with camouflaged at 39m/sec basic wind speed.

(Table-1 and 2) Monopole Capacity according to TIA-222-H without Camouflaged and with Camouflaged

Monopole Capacity according TIA-222-H

Pole shape section	=	ROUND
Yield strength, F_y	=	345 N/mm ²
Elastic Modulus, E	=	200000 N/mm ²
0.114 E / F_y	=	66.087
0.448 E / F_y	=	259.71
0.0714 E / F_y	=	41.391
0.309 E / F_y	=	179.13
ϕ_c	=	0.9
ϕ_t	=	0.9
ϕ_v	=	0.9

Elevation (m)	Outer Diameter of Pole (mm)	Wall Thickness of pole (mm)	Inner Diameter of Pole (mm)	Pipe Area (mm ²)	Factored Axial Load (kN)	Factored Shear Load (kN)	Factored Bending Moment (kN-m)	Plastic Section Modulus, Z (mm ³)	Elastic Section Modulus, S (mm ³)	F_y	D/t	$\phi_c + P_x$	$\phi_t + M_x$	$\phi_v + V_x$	Interaction Equation
0.00-12.00	1000	5	990	15629	52.08	44.72	1150	4950166.7	3868477.67	268	200.00	3768.41	1148.94	1884.20	1.001
12.00-24.00	725	5	715	11310	34.79	35.26	524.26	2592041.7	2021809.87	282	145.00	2873.22	804.83	1436.61	0.651
24.00-30.00	475	5	465	7382.7	22.28	26.86	151.59	1104541.7	858438.126	310	95.00	2058.38	536.75	1029.19	0.282

Monopole Capacity according TIA-222-H

Pole shape section	=	ROUND
Yield strength, F_y	=	345 N/mm ²
Elastic Modulus, E	=	200000 N/mm ²
0.114 E / F_y	=	66.087
0.448 E / F_y	=	259.71
0.0714 E / F_y	=	41.391
0.309 E / F_y	=	179.13
ϕ_c	=	0.9
ϕ_t	=	0.9
ϕ_v	=	0.9

Elevation (m)	Outer Diameter of Pole (mm)	Wall Thickness of pole (mm)	Inner Diameter of Pole (mm)	Pipe Area (mm ²)	Factored Axial Load (kN)	Factored Shear Load (kN)	Factored Bending Moment (kN-m)	Plastic Section Modulus, Z (mm ³)	Elastic Section Modulus, S (mm ³)	F_y	D/t	$\phi_c + P_x$	$\phi_t + M_x$	$\phi_v + V_x$	Interaction Equation
0.00-12.00	1000	5	990	15629	70.08	28.82	505.93	4950166.7	3868477.67	268	200.00	3768.41	1148.94	1884.20	0.440
12.00-24.00	725	5	715	11310	52.79	19.36	216.85	2592041.7	2021809.87	282	145.00	2873.22	804.83	1436.61	0.269
24.00-30.00	475	5	465	7382.7	40.28	10.96	34.95	1104541.7	858438.126	310	95.00	2058.38	536.75	1029.19	0.065

Table 1 (fig.3) and Table 2 (fig.4) Structural steel Pole Moment capacity Vs Max Pole bending Moment for Monopole without camouflaged tower and with camouflaged.

(Height = 30m and basic wind speed = 39m/sec)

From Table 6 (fig.6) it was observed that for a 30m tower height monopole without camouflaged with 39m/sec basic wind speed, structural steel Max Monopole Moment is more than Pole Moment capacity and interaction equation stress ratio is more than 1 from elevation (0 to 12m) height of tower that means monopole without camouflaged is not safe.

From Table 7 (fig.7) it was observed that for a 30m tower height monopole with camouflaged with 39m/sec basic wind speed, structural steel Max Monopole Moment is less than Pole Moment capacity and interaction equation stress ratio is less than 1 throughout its height that means monopole with camouflaged is safe.

VI. CONCLUSION

The study indicates that monopoles featuring camouflage at the top exhibit reduced lateral displacements compared to the permissible limits for equivalent height and loading conditions. In contrast, monopoles lacking camouflage at the top demonstrate lateral displacements that exceed the allowable thresholds.

Specifically, for a monopole tower with a height of 30 meters and a basic wind speed of 39 m/sec, the maximum moment experienced by the structural steel of the non-camouflaged monopole surpasses the pole moment capacity, resulting in an interaction equation stress ratio greater than 1 from the elevation of 0 to 12 meters. This finding suggests that the non-camouflaged monopole is structurally unsafe. Conversely, the camouflaged monopole of the

same height and wind speed shows a maximum moment that is below the pole moment capacity, with an interaction equation stress ratio consistently less than 1 throughout its height, indicating that it is structurally safe. Furthermore, the presence of camouflage at the top enhances the load-carrying capacity of the camouflaged monopole, as all antennas are shielded from wind exposure. Given these observations and conclusions, it is advisable to implement monopoles with camouflage, as they demonstrate superior structural capacity and maintain lateral displacements below the allowable limits. A future study can extend the design of camouflaged monopole against vortex shedding vibration.

References:

- [1]. Bryan Keith, Study: The Improvement of Strength and Stiffness Capabilities of steel multi-sector monopoly towers using reinforced carbon fiber polymers as a retrofitting mechanism, North Carolina, State University, Southern Carolina,
- [2]. Daniel Horn, â Monopole Bases design in English, Technical Guide 1, AISC.Boulder, C., Personal Communications, Kaufman, Rocky Mountain Research Laboratories, 1992. Jeneevan: — Steel Towers Subject Strength Assessment, Civil Engineering Department, 2011 C.J. Kaufman.
- [3]. R. P Rokade, Journal for Research into Structural Engineering, 5 August 2011. Comparative studies of traditional monopolies and the microwave in towers every day.
- [4]. Shen-En Chen, â Two Pole Operating Power Transmission Modal Features from North Carolina University, 2010 â Civil and Environmental Engineering Department.
- [5]. Siddesha.H, — Microwave Applied Research Engineering Towers Speed, Volume 1, No. 3, 2010.
- [6]. CSC Siting Council of Connecticut. Facilities for Telecommunications. Version II, USA; 2017.Saeed Alsamhi.
- [7]. Government of NSW. Telecommunications structure guidelines. Telco Authority, United States; 2015.
- [8]. Masts and Towers. Ulrik Støttrup-Andersen. Department Head of Market, Denmark, 2009. 2009.Florea Dinu. Sustainable buildings amid natural hazards and disaster. European Erasmus [3] Universitatea Politehnica Timisoara, Master, Lecture 18: Towers, chimneys; 2014.
- [9]. The past, present and future of Smith BW and Støttrup-Andersen U. Tourers and masts. IASS Conference, Madrid, Spain; 1997. 1997.
- [10]. U. Masts and Towers for the UMTS network in Sweden, Støttrup-Andersen. Euro Steel, Netherlands Maastricht; 2005.
- [11]. Stott up-Andersen U. Masts and Tower Analysis and Design. Structural International Congress, San Francisco, USA; 1998.
- [12]. IE 1991-1-4: 2007 [7] Eurocode 1: Structure activities — General actions Part 1-4: wind measures (EC1-1-4). United States; 2010. 10.
- [13]. EN 1993-3-1: Eurocode 3 - Structures of steel - Part 3-1: Towers, masts and fireplaces - Towers and masts. United States; 2009.

- [14]. EN 1993-1-1: Steel structure design Part 1-1: general construction regulations and guidelines. United States; 2005. CHS versus different cross-section performance assessment. USA; 2016. Ferreira. Chapter 3.
- [15]. Nielsen MG. Benefits from the use of telecommunications structure tubular profiles. 11th Tubular Structures International Symposium, Quebec, Canada; 2006.
- [16]. B.M. Broderick, Department of Civil, Structural, and Environmental Engineering at Trinity College, Dublin, April 18, Simple models for natural frequencies, and mode forms of utility towers. B. Lanier,
—Compliance with CFRP high module steel monopolies in the field of materials in Germany, Journal of thin-walled structures, 2009.
- [17] Abdulkadir M. Tah, Kamiran M. Alsilevanai, Mustafa Özakça (4th February 2017), “Comparison of Various Bracing System for Self-Supporting Steel Lattice Structure Towers”, Turkey. American Journal of Civil Engineering. Vol. 5, No. 2, 2017, pp.60-68, ISSN: 2330-8729 (Print); ISSN: 2330-8737 (Online).
- [18] Marcel Isandro R. de Oliveira, José Guilherme S. da Silva, April-June 2007, “Structural Analysis of Guyed Steel Telecommunication Towers for Radio Antennas”, Vol. XXIX, No. 2.
- [19] Roy Butler, July 2014, “Choosing a Wind Turbine Tower”, Issue #161.
- [20] Haiyan Long, Geir Moe and Tim Fischer, December 2011, “Lattice Towers for Bottom-Fixed Offshore Wind Turbines in the Ultimate Limit State: Variation of Some Geometric Parameters” J. Offshore Mech. Arct. Eng 134(2), 021202.
- [21] Prof. S. R. Satish Kumar and Prof. A. R. Santha Kumar, “Design of Steel Structures”, India. Indian Institute of Technology Madras.
- [22] American tower. Collocation Considerations & Best Practices for Financial Services Orgs. A structural engineering perspective. Available at: http://www.americantower.com/Assets/uploads/files/PDFs/American_Tower_Financial_Services_Collocation_Best_Practices.pdf. Accessed 2017.
- [23] European Committee for Standardization, 2005. “Eurocode 3 design of steel structure’s part 3–1: towers, masts and chimneys towers and masts”, Brussels.
- [24] TIA/EIA-222-G, (Draft). Structural Standards for Antenna Supporting Structures and Antennas.